

Optimal Data Fusion strategies Using Multiple-Sensor Detection Systems

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Abstract

The problem of decision fusion in distributed sensor systems is considered. Distributed sensors pass their decisions to a fusion center that combines the received decisions from the various sensors into a final global decision. The case where only two sensors are combined using an AND fusion rule was analyzed by Kovattana [1], and the cases where two and three sensors are combined using AND and OR fusion rules were analyzed by Fefjar [2]. Stearns considered the case of combining two sensors using AND and OR fusion rules and showed that the receiver operating characteristics of the AND and the OR combiners must be intersected, AND was superior to OR at low false-alarm probabilities, and OR was superior to AND at high false-alarm probabilities. This paper shows that the optimal fusion rule does not only depend on the desired false alarm probability and the signal to noise ratio but also depends on the probability distribution function.

1 Introduction

The problem of multiple-sensor in surveillance purposes has attracted the attention of several investigators. This interest has been sparked by the requirement of military surveillance systems to be more reliable and immune to electronic attack than single sensor systems. This can be achieved by properly combining the information obtained from n various sensors. The sensors are allowed to derive local decisions u_i 's, $i=1,2, \dots, n$, and a fusion center is responsible for combining the received decisions into a final global decision u_0 . According to Neyman-Pearson criterion, it is required to find the optimal fusion rule of the fusion center that maximizes the global detection probability (PD) for a desired global false alarm probability

(PF).

The usual fusion rule is implemented as k -out-of- n majority-rule voting. This means that the fusion center adopts hypothesis H_1 (presence of a target) as the true hypothesis when at least k -sensor favors that hypothesis. Two special cases are AND fusion rule, corresponding to setting $k = n$, and OR fusion rule, corresponding to setting $k = 1$.

The AND combiner was analyzed by Kovattana [1] for the case of two sensors and the global performance was obtained assuming event conditional independence. The AND and The OR combiners were later compared by Fefjar [2] for the cases of two and three sensors. Fefjar showed that OR fusion rule was always superior to AND fusion rule. Stearns [3] showed that depending on the choice of the global false alarm probability, either AND or OR combining can be better. Stearns [3] claimed that the AND and the OR global performances must be intersected, AND was superior to OR at low false-alarm probabilities, and OR was superior to AND at high false-alarm probabilities. It will be shown that, depending on the operating point on the global receiver operating characteristic (ROC) and on the parameters of the probability distributions under hypothesis, either AND or OR can be better at either low or high global false alarm probabilities. Furthermore, the AND and the OR combiners may not be intersected at all.

2 Optimal Data Fusion Using Two Non-Identical Sensors

Consider any two sensors with ROC s, $p_{D1} = g(p_{F1})$ and $p_{D2} = h(p_{F2})$. To derive the optimum threshold setting for each sensor, we will assume that the sensor's decisions are conditionally independent given the hypothesis. In case of AND fusion rule, the global false

alarm and detection probabilities are given by :

$$PF = p_{F1} p_{F2}, \quad (1)$$

$$PD = p_{D1} p_{D2}. \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) can be rewritten as :

$$PD = g(p_{F1}) h(p_{F2}) \quad (3)$$

Substitution for p_{F2} from (1), we obtain

$$PD(PF) = g(p_{F1}) h\left(\frac{PF}{p_{F1}}\right), \quad (4)$$

where the dependence $PD(PF)$ is called the global *ROC* of the considered distributed detection system. Clearly from (2), $p_{F1} > PF$, and (3) will be

$$PD(PF) = \sup_{p_{F1} < PF} \left(g(p_{F1}) h\left(\frac{PF}{p_{F1}}\right) \right). \quad (5)$$

In the case of OR fusion rule, we have

$$PF = p_{F1} + p_{F2}(1 - p_{F1}), \quad (6)$$

which yields

$$p_{F2} = \frac{(PF - p_{F1})}{(1 - p_{F1})}, \quad (7)$$

From (6), $p_{F1} < PF$, and the optimum global *ROC* using an OR combiner is defined as :

$$\sup_{0 < p_{F1} < PF} \{g(p_{F1}) + h(\alpha) - g(p_{F1})h(\alpha)\}, \quad (8)$$

where

$$\alpha = \frac{PF - p_{F1}}{1 - p_{F1}}. \quad (9)$$

3 Optimal Data Fusion Using Identical Sensors

If the two sensors have identical *ROC*s, i.e.

$$g(p_{F1}) = h(p_{F2}), \quad (10)$$

then symmetry can be invoked to yield the following results

$$AND : PD(PF) = g^2(\sqrt{PF}), \quad (11)$$

$$OR : PD(PF) = 2g(\beta) - g^2(\beta), \quad (12)$$

where

$$\beta = 1 - \sqrt{1 - PF}. \quad (13)$$

The extension of the two non-identical sensors case to the case of three or more non-identical sensors is

complicated. However, the special case of n -identical sensors is important since the global optimization of the whole distributed detection system (the threshold's setting plus the fusion center) is straightforward. We now extend the above results to an n -sensor case [5]-[7]. The PF and the PD are given by :

$$PF = \sum_{i=k}^n c_i^n p_F^i (1 - p_F)^{n-i}, \quad (14)$$

$$PD = \sum_{i=k}^n c_i^n p_D^i (1 - p_D)^{n-i}, \quad (15)$$

where

$$c_i^n = \frac{n!}{i!(n-i)!}. \quad (16)$$

For $k=1$, the optimum fusion rule reduces to an OR fusion rule, while for $k=n$ it becomes an AND fusion rule. For a specified value of PF , there is an optimum integer k that maximizes the PD . This is called k -out-of- n fusion rule. This means that if k or more sensors decide hypothesis H_1 , then the global decision will be H_1 , i.e.

$$u_0 = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \sum_{i=1}^n u_i < k \\ 1 & \text{if } \sum_{i=1}^n u_i \geq k \end{cases}, \quad (17)$$

where the u_i 's, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ are the individual sensor decisions, and u_0 is the global decision of the fusion center.

4 Performance Optimization Examples

Stearns [3] considered the case of combining two identical sensors with Gaussian distributed observations (the case of detecting a constant in Gaussian noise). His claim about the intersection of the AND and the OR combiners and the superiority of the AND at low false alarm probabilities and the OR at high false alarm probabilities are valid in the particular example which he had considered. In general, this is not true. Here we consider the case of exponentially distributed observations; the cases of n -identical sensors and two non-identical sensors are considered :

$$f(y_i|H_0) = \exp(-y_i), \quad (18)$$

$$f(y_i|H_1) = \lambda_i \exp(-d_i y_i), \lambda_i > 0, y_i > 0 \quad i = 1, \dots, n, \quad (19)$$

$$f(y_i|H_j) = 0, y_i < 0, i = 1, \dots, n, j = 0, 1, \quad (20)$$

Notice that the observations are independent when conditioned on H . The Likelihood ratio of the detectors is given by :

$$L(y_i) = \frac{f(y_i|H_1)}{f(y_i|H_0)} = \frac{d_i \exp(-d_i y_i)}{\exp(-y_i)}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n. \quad (21)$$

The decision rules of the detectors are given by :

$$u_i = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } L(y_i) = \frac{f(y_i|H_1)}{f(y_i|H_0)} < \lambda_i \\ 1 & \text{if } L(y_i) = \frac{f(y_i|H_1)}{f(y_i|H_0)} \geq \lambda_i. \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

which reduces to

$$u_i = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } y_i < \frac{1}{1-d_i} \ln\left(\frac{\lambda_i}{d_i}\right). \\ 1 & \text{if } y_i \geq \frac{1}{1-d_i} \ln\left(\frac{\lambda_i}{d_i}\right), \quad d_i < 1, \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

$$u_i = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } y_i \geq \frac{1}{1-d_i} \ln\left(\frac{\lambda_i}{d_i}\right). \\ 1 & \text{if } y_i < \frac{1}{1-d_i} \ln\left(\frac{\lambda_i}{d_i}\right), \quad d_i > 1. \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

The corresponding false alarm and detection probabilities are given by :

$$p_{Fi} = \left(\frac{d_i}{\lambda_i}\right)^{\frac{1}{1-d_i}}, \quad (25)$$

$$p_{Di} = \left(\frac{d_i}{\lambda_i}\right)^{\frac{d_i}{1-d_i}}, \quad d_i < 1, \quad (26)$$

$$p_{Fi} = 1 - \left(\frac{\lambda_i}{d_i}\right)^{\frac{1}{d_i-1}}, \quad (27)$$

$$p_{Di} = 1 - \left(\frac{\lambda_i}{d_i}\right)^{\frac{d_i}{d_i-1}}, \quad d_i > 1. \quad (28)$$

Hence the ROC s of the detectors can be written as :

$$p_{Di} = p_{Fi}^{d_i} = g(p_{Fi}), \quad d_i < 1, \quad (29)$$

$$p_{Di} = 1 - (1 - p_{Di})^{d_i} = h(p_{Fi}), \quad d_i > 1. \quad (30)$$

Figure 1 compares the ROC s of the OR and the AND combiners as well as the individual sensor's ROC s in case of two non-identical sensors with $d_1 = 0.4$ and $d_2 = 2.5$. The global performance improvement of the OR and the AND fusion rules over the individual sensor's ROC s is obvious. Figure 1 shows an intersection of the OR and the AND ROC s. In this figure, the AND combiner is superior to OR at low PF s and the OR combiner is superior to AND at high PF s. The choice between them is determined by the specified PF .

Figure 1: Comparison of ROC s of two different sensors, $d_1=0.4$, $d_2=2.5$.

Figures 2-5 compare the OR and the AND combiners for the case of two identical sensors with exponentially distributed observations for different values of coefficient d (let $d_1 = d_2 = d$). Figures 2 and 4 consider the case when $d < 1$ while Figures 3 and 5 consider the case when $d > 1$. It is clear that when $d < 1$, the OR combiner is optimum for all values of PF s while when $d > 1$, the AND combiner is optimum for all values of PF s. It is also clear that there is no intersections of the OR and the AND ROC s in these figures.

Figure 2: Comparison of ROC s of two identical sensors, coefficient $d = 0.2$.

Figures 6-9 compare the global ROC s of the k - out of n fusion rules for different values of d for the case of n -identical sensors. Figures 6 and 8 show the case

Figure 3: Comparison of ROCs of two identical sensors, coefficient $d = 4$

Figure 5: Comparison of ROCs of two identical sensors, coefficient $d = 8.5$

Figure 4: Comparison of ROCs of two identical sensors, coefficient $d = 0.08$.

Figure 6: Comparison of ROCs of three identical sensors, coefficient $d = 0.25$.

when $d < 1$ in case of three and five identical sensors, and Figures 7 and 9 show the case when $d > 1$. Figures 6-9 lead to the same conclusions as above.

From Figures 2-9, it is clear that the optimum fusion rule depends only on the coefficient of the probability distributions d . It is also clear that depending on the coefficient d , either the AND or the OR combiner can be superior for all values of PFs . Furthermore, it is clear that the ROC s of the OR and the AND combiners may not be intersected. From the above results, we remark that (1) the AND combiner is not always optimum at low PFs , (2) the OR combiner is not always optimum at high PFs , (3) the choice between the AND and the OR combiners depends on the

desired values of PFs as well as the coefficient of the probability distributions (d in our examples), and (4) the ROC s of the OR and the AND combiners may not be intersected at all.

5 Conclusion

Optimum fusion rules for multiple sensor distributed detection systems have been considered. For the case of exponentially distributed observations, the optimal fusion rule is based on the value of d . For $d < 1$, the OR fusion rule is found to be optimal whereas the AND fusion rule is optimal for $d > 1$. The choice between them depends on the desired global false alarm probability as well as the parameters of the probability distributions under both hypotheses.

Figure 7: Comparison of ROCs of three identical sensors, coefficient $d = 3.5$.

Figure 9: Comparison of ROCs of five identical sensors, coefficient $d = 4.5$.

Figure 8: Comparison of ROCs of five identical sensors, coefficient $d = 0.3$

Furthermore, the global ROCs of the OR and the AND combiners may or may not be intersected. This again depends on the coefficients of the probability distribution function.

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